

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE SKILLS FOR EFL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH CLASSES

U.K. Akhmedova

Urgench State University, English Language Lecturer

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15483871>

Abstract. *The article focuses on Project-Based Learning (PBL) as an instructional approach that promotes hands-on meaningful learning for EFL students and permits them to connect what they learn in the classroom to real life, along with opportunities to develop the four main language skills and subskills in the contextualized and integrated way. The purpose of this article is to understand the EFL students' perceptions regarding PBL and its contribution to their learning of English as a Foreign Language through their own experiences.*

Keywords: *project based learning (PBL), language skills, English as a Foreign Language (EFL), adult learner, interactive activities, learning process, instructional approach, motivation.*

Introduction.

In modern society, the importance of learning English cannot be denied or ignored, as English is the most widely spoken language globally. Learning English requires constant practice and patience. However, among adult students, there is often a feeling that achieving fluency in English is impossible.

Currently, most English as a foreign language (EFL) class for university students do not meet their needs. Knowles (1973) explained that adult students want the time spent in the classroom to be as useful as possible, not only for them as learners but also as individuals. He also noted that adult students turn to educational activities largely because they feel some inadequacy in how they are handling the current challenges of life. They want to apply what they learn today to their lives tomorrow, so the concept of time is linked to immediate application. Consequently, they approach education with a focus on problem-solving during the learning process. Therefore, English as a foreign language (EFL) class should provide students with the necessary tools to connect what they learn in the classroom with the real world and make the time spent in class meaningful and beneficial. Knowles refers to Lindeman's (1970) assumptions that adult learners can learn most effectively when allowed to "take control of their learning process" (Barker, Sterdevant, & Smith, 1999, p. 21). Lindeman's assumptions, as reported by Knowles (1970), are as follows:

a) Adults are motivated to learn because they experience needs and interests that learning will satisfy; therefore, these are suitable starting points for organizing educational activities for adults.

b) Adults orientation toward learning is connected to their life goals; therefore, appropriate units for organizing adult education are life situations, not subjects.

c) Experience is the richest resource for adult learning; therefore, the primary methodology of adult education is the analysis of experience.

d) Adults have a deep need for independence; therefore, the teacher's role is to explore with them, rather than to transfer knowledge and then assess their conformity to it.

e) Individual differences between people increase with age; therefore, adult education should provide optimal opportunities for differences in style, time, place, and pace of learning.

Definitely, the above assumptions support the idea that English language teachers for adults should provide students with more practical learning experiences. English language teachers for adults can create such practical experiences by designing meaningful, engaging, and interactive lessons that place students at the center of the learning process.

Certainly, Project-Based Learning (PBL) is a teaching methodology that is said to allow EFL learners to apply all the aforementioned benefits in practice in a meaningful context. In a project-based learning environment, English learners work mainly in groups and actively participate in the learning process. In other words, students step out of their passive comfort zones and become active by starting the learning process and carrying out their projects (Dewey, 1938).

For example, students interact with their groupmates by exchanging, discussing, debating, and organizing ideas to develop their projects (Blumenfeld, Soloway, Marx, Krajick, Guzdial, & Palinscar, 1991). As a result, they create something new that they have thought through and planned in advance. Thus, Project-Based Learning (PBL) fosters students' creativity during the process of working on their projects.

Project-Based Learning (PBL) can also help increase motivation for English as a foreign language (EFL) students, as it aligns with their learning styles and preferences, allowing them to utilize their abilities and learning styles in the most suitable way for them (Fleming, 2000; Jakar, 2006; McGrath, 2002; Solomon, 2003; Stoller, 2006). Furthermore, in a Project-Based Learning environment, all four major language skills and their subgroups can be integrated, providing a more comprehensive learning experience for those studying English as a foreign language.

Materials and Methods

The purpose of this article is to explore the perceptions of adult English as a foreign language (EFL) students regarding Project-Based Learning (PBL) and its contribution to their English learning based on their personal experiences. Since this research aims to present the experiences of students who have actually participated in Project-Based Learning (PBL) activities, the method of in-depth phenomenological interviews was chosen for this understanding, which is a qualitative approach. Both qualitative and quantitative approaches in second language teaching (TESOL) research have historically been significant. However, since 1994, the number of qualitative studies has significantly increased (Chapelle & Duff, 2003; Cumming, 1994; Seliger & Shohamy, 1989).

Both qualitative and quantitative research have characteristics that can be useful in the field of TESOL. Qualitative research allows the researcher to analyze the phenomenon as a whole, while quantitative research examines the parts (variables) of that phenomenon (Merriam, 1998). Both approaches can be used to describe a learning situation (Hadfield, 2002). Since the aim of this study is to analyze the phenomenon of Project-Based Learning (PBL) among adult students of English as a second language as a whole, rather than its individual components, a qualitative approach was chosen.

Results and Discussion.

The purpose of this article is to understand the perceptions of English as a foreign language (EFL) students regarding their participation in project work as the primary activity in a Project-Based Learning (PBL) program. The results of the study are presented in six sections:

1. Characteristics of the participants;
2. Projects and language skills: Are there any connections?

3. Projects in the classroom: Experience;
4. Projects outside the classroom: What are they useful for?
5. Projects: I want to speak, but I'm afraid;
6. Projects: Do I actually like them?

The first section presents the characteristics of the participants. The second section presents the results of the research on what participants think about the projects in terms of learning English. The third section discusses the process of developing projects and the interaction of participants with their peers while working in groups. This section also describes participants' experiences with the projects they developed, starting from the moment they decided what to do or when the teacher introduced the idea of the project they were going to work on.

The fourth section discusses the participants' perceptions of the usefulness of the projects in their personal lives, including three categories of topics: helping others, contributing to their own life, and what they learned from the projects. The fifth section describes the participants' fears about public speaking. Finally, the sixth section presents the opinions, agreements, and disagreements of the participants regarding projects as a teaching method, as well as their recommendations for English as a second language (ESL) teachers to create a positive experience using projects for students.

Conclusion

The aim of this article was to explore adult English as a foreign language (EFL) students' perception of their experiences with Project-Based Learning (PBL). The participants of this study were adult EFL students from Uzbek universities offering curricula with a project-based approach to learning. My interest in this research stems from the fact that Project-Based Learning (PBL) offers English as a second or foreign language students an active teaching methodology. As a former student of English as a foreign language myself, I believe that learning English as a foreign or second language is better achieved when what students learn is useful, meaningful, and can be applied in their real lives beyond the classroom. Based on this, I decided to conduct research that would help me explore what it was like to participate in project-based lessons from the students' perspective. I wanted to hear from adult English language students about their impressions of Project-Based Learning (PBL) as a teaching methodology. My need to study their experiences led me to listen to their stories through in-depth phenomenological interviews over several weeks.

My conclusions were based on the narratives of the participants about their own experiences with the phenomenon. After thoroughly examining the interview results, two main themes emerged. The first theme is the students' perception of Project-Based Learning (PBL) as a teaching methodology and the contribution they see in it to their learning of English as a foreign language. The second theme is the recommendations or objections of students regarding the implementation of Project-Based Learning (PBL).

This research has been both a rewarding and challenging task, and it has allowed me to understand the impression that Project-Based Learning (PBL) makes on a group of English as some foreign language students. It has also been a challenge for me, as it forced me to rethink my practice as an English as a foreign language teacher.

After several years devoted to this research, its results will help me return to the classroom with a more student-oriented approach. I believe that my students and I can work together to find the best ways to meet their educational needs and provide educational practices that will help them maximize their potential.

REFERENCES

1. Adderley, K., Ashwin, C, Bradbury, P., Freeman, J., Goodlad, S., Greene, J., Jenkins, D., Rae, J., & Uren, O. *The project method in higher education*. London: Society for Research into Higher Education Ltd. 1975-p56
2. Akhmedova, U. (2022). "Methods for Integrating Creativity into Project-Based Learning (PBL) for Teaching Foreign Languages to University Students." *Archive of Scientific Research*, 2(1). Retrieved from. <https://journal.tsue.uz/index.php/archive/article/view/2162>
3. Akhmedova, Ugiljon Kuronboevna (2020). "Developing 21st Century Skills of Foreign Language Learners through Project-Based Learning (PBL).," *Scientific and Technical Journal of Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology*: Vol. 2: Iss. 7, Article 51. Available at: <https://namdu.researchcommons.org/journal/vol2/iss7/51>
4. Barker, T. S., Sturdivant, V. A., Smith, H. W., Jr. *Adult students in the college classroom*. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 434631), P. 1999
5. Beckett, G. H. Teacher and student evaluations of project-based instruction. *TESL Canada Journal*, 19(2), 2002, P. 52-56.
6. Beckett, G. H., & Miller, P. C. *Project-based second and foreign language education. Past, present, and future*. Greenwich, CT: Information Age Publishing. 2006, P.23
7. Ermetova Jamila "Synchronic and Diachronic approaches to the study some problems of English punctuation", 2021.
8. Jamol Jalolov, "Methods of Teaching Foreign Languages." – Tashkent: 2012, P. 45.
9. Ochilov M. New pedagogical technologies. - Karshi. Nasaf. 2000, P.87
10. Tolipov U.K., Usmanbayeva M. Pedagogical technology: theory and practice. Monograph. Tashkent: 2005.P.23